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Zinc-substituted hydroxyapatite-bacteriophage complexes for complementary antibacterial properties

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Phase-pure HAp nanoparticles containing up to 0.8 wt% of Zn were synthesized.
- Zn confers antibacterial activity of HAp against *S. aureus*.
- After incubation with HAp nanoparticles, phages retain activity against host bacteria.
- Phages confer antibacterial activity of HAp against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The increasing resistance of bacteria to antibiotics poses a significant threat to human health. Therefore, new treatment options, including alternative antimicrobial agents, are being sought. Taking into account that the combination of bacteriophages with antibacterial metal ions could provide a synergistic effect, as well as the extensive use of hydroxyapatite (HAp) in the development of bone implant materials, Zn-substituted HAp (ZnHAp) nanoparticles' interaction with bacteriophages was evaluated for the first time. The physicochemical and antibacterial properties of the ZnHAp nanoparticles were characterized. Pure-phase HAp nanoparticles with Zn content up to 0.74 ± 0.07 wt% were synthesized using wet chemical precipitation. The ZnHAp nanoparticles did not show antibacterial activity against Gram-negative *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*) bacteria. In turn, the ZnHAp nanoparticles' antibacterial activity against Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) bacteria depended on the Zn concentration and the incubation time - the highest efficiency was shown by the HAp nanoparticles with 0.74 ± 0.07 wt% of Zn after 72 h. *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* bacteriophages retained lytic activity after incubation in the presence of the nanoparticles, showing activity against host bacteria, i.e., a moderate titer (10^6 - 10^8 PFU/mL), yet corresponding to an effective therapeutic titer both in the bacteriophage

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suspension and sediments after decantation. The current findings illustrated that combining lytic phages with metallic ions substituted HAp nanoparticles is a promising technique for obtaining novel biomaterials with the prevention and treatment potential of polymicrobial and biofilm infections.

1. Introduction

Implant-related infections are among the most severe healthcare problems, often leading to implant replacement, amputation, or even the death of the patient [1]. Gram-positive cocci are the most frequently isolated microorganisms in the infected areas [2]. Among Gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) colonizes almost all medical implants, as they have a strong adhesion force that increases the tendency to form biofilms [1]. Gram-negative bacteria are responsible for 10–23 % of all infections, most commonly causing acute and polymicrobial infections. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*) accounts for 5–20 % of Gram-negative infections. It is considered one of the most challenging bacteria to fight due to its resistance to many drugs and its ability to form particularly resistant mechanisms such as biofilms and small colonies [2]. Thus, the increasing resistance of bacteria to antibiotics poses a significant threat to human health, leading to the search for new treatment options, including alternative antimicrobial agents such as bacteriophages, which are natural enemies of bacteria [3]. Moreover, *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* are the predominant bacterial targets of personalized bacteriophage therapy for difficult-to-treat infections [4].

Bacteriophages, or phages, are viruses that are almost 50 times smaller than bacteria and can infect and kill them [5,6]. Phages have all the characteristics of viruses – they have relatively small genomes, high selectivity, and use host mechanisms to replicate [7]. Thus, phages are a promising weapon in the fight against antibiotic-resistant, pathogenic, and biofilm-forming bacteria. Several phage therapy routes (e.g., oral, intravenous, and topical) exist. Delivering phages as close as possible to the site of infection to achieve the desired concentration is challenging [5,8]. Intravenous phage therapy, administered by blood to areas that cannot be reached by topical or oral treatment, is most often used to treat systemic or implant-related infections [7,8]. The disadvantage of this route is that phages are cleared from the bloodstream within 1–3 h [7]. Phages are also limited by their low stability and high environmental sensitivity. Combining phages with biomaterials (e.g., nanoparticles, ceramics, hydrogels) can stabilize them, protect them against several harmful factors, and provide a controlled release for long-term therapeutic effects [9,10]. Phages can be embedded, encapsulated, and surface adsorbed [8–10].

Among others, hydroxyapatite (HAp) has been observed to stabilize phage activity over time at different pH levels, making the HAp-phage complex suitable for long-term treatment and infection control in both acidic (stomach, urinary tract) and physiological (blood) environments [10]. HAp is widely used in the medical industry as bone implant materials, including coatings on implants, tissue engineering scaffolds, and drug delivery agents [11]. Thus, HAp could be an excellent phage carrier for bone implant materials. However, only a few studies on HAp and phage combinations are available. Meurice et al. proposed *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) bacteriophages (λ_{vir}) in combination with HAp and β -tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP) ceramic pellets as prophylactic treatments for bone repair [12]. Fulgione et al. have evaluated the HAp nanoparticles as carriers for *Salmonella* bacteriophages (SR Φ 1) [10]. Despite promising results, there is concern that phage alone could develop phage-resistant bacteria. To avoid this, the synergy of phages with various antimicrobial agents, such as antibiotics and metallic ions, is being investigated [13]. It has been reported that adding Ca^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions in different concentrations to the phage cocktail (PHB22a, PHB25a, PHB38a, PHB40a) can improve the antibacterial effect against *S. aureus* bacteria and lower their biofilm-forming activity [14]. On the other hand, in blood and similar environments and conditions, Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} ,

and Fe^{2+} ions are necessary for phages to act against *E. coli* bacteria effectively. In the presence of Ca^{2+} ions, the phage titer is increased, and the interaction of the phage with the host is improved [15]. Mn^{2+} ions improve the antibiofilm activity of the phage and its endolysin (lys08) against *Enterococcus faecalis* (*E. faecalis*) biofilms [16]. Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} ions improve phage lysis and increase titer and adsorption [15,17]. Both Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions are essential in phage proliferation as they stabilize deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) in the phage capsid and control DNA entry into the bacterial cell [17].

In this study, the interaction of metallic ions substituted, specifically, Zn-substituted HAp (Zn-HAp) nanoparticles with *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* phages was assessed for the first time. Emphasis was placed on the influence of different stages of preparation on the components and the nanoparticle-phage complexes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Synthesis

The HAp and Zn-HAp powders were synthesized using a wet chemical precipitation method [18]. The precipitation reaction was carried out in the laboratory reactor IKA EUROSTAR Power Control-Visc P7 (Ika-Werke, Germany) equipped with an anchor stirrer. For the HAp synthesis, deionized H_2O (0.55 μ S/m, Adrona Crystal, Latvia) was filled in the laboratory reactor, and CaO (95.0–100.5 %, Jost Chemicals Co., MO, USA) (calcined in a muffle furnace (Nabertherm LHT 08/16, Nabertherm, Germany) at 1100 °C for 1 h) was added and stirred for approximately 1 h at 100 rpm to obtain homogenous suspension. The Zn-HAp powders (with nominal Zn content 1 wt% (1ZnHAp) and 2 wt% (2ZnHAp)) were synthesized by adding ZnO (99–100.5 %, Sigma Aldrich, Germany) and, simultaneously, reducing the amount of CaO in the starting suspension. (Ca+Zn)/P molar ratio in the starting suspension was 1.67. The amounts of raw materials used in the syntheses are shown in Table 1.

After 1 h, the obtained suspension was heated to 45 °C using a hot plate RCT basic (IKA, Germany), a temperature sensor, and a water bath. Upon reaching 45 °C, the 2 M H_3PO_4 (75 %, Latvijas kimija Ltd., Latvia) aqueous solution was added to the starting suspension at a rate of 1 mL/min using the automatic dosing system TITRONIC® universal (Schott, The Netherlands). After adding the stoichiometric (i.e., (Ca+Zn)/P molar ratio) amount of the 2 M H_3PO_4 aqueous solution, the mixture was stirred for about 1 h to complete the reaction, and the precipitates were left to age overnight. The suspension was re-stirred and filtered with a vacuum filtration system (Bunsen flask, Buchner funnel, and vacuum pump). The filtered paste was oven-dried at 105 °C for 24 h. The dried product was then crushed into a fine powder using a pestle and mortar. The ground powder was steam-sterilized at 121 °C for 20 min (with a drying step of 45 min) using an autoclave Tuttnauer (Elara 11, the Netherlands) to evaluate the effect on the physicochemical properties and for microbiological tests.

Table 1
Amounts of the raw materials used in syntheses.

Sample series	HAp	1ZnHAp	2ZnHAp
Deionized H_2O , mL	2000		
CaO, g	16.80	16.72	16.62
ZnO, g	0	0.15	0.30
2 M H_3PO_4	89.80	89.80	89.80

2.2. Physicochemical characterization

2.2.1. Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry

The Ca, Zn, and P concentrations were measured using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). Samples for testing were dissolved in a high-purity HNO₃ solution (65 %, ChemLab, Belgium) and diluted with deionized water (Millipore Synergy 185, Germany). The vessels with samples were kept at room temperature for at least 20 min to complete the reaction, then capped and transferred to a microwave oven Mars 6 (CEM Corporation, NC, USA) for digestion. The temperature was raised to 150 °C within 30 min, and the samples were held at 150 °C for 30 min. After cooling, the samples were filtered through a filter with 12–15 μm pore size (Filtres Fionori, France), quantitatively transferred to volumetric flasks, and diluted to 50 mL volume with deionized water. An ICP-MS instrument Agilent 7700x (Agilent Technologies, CA, USA) with Mass Hunter Workstation software version B.01.03 (Tokyo, Japan) for ICP-MS was used to measure the Ca, Zn, and P concentration.

2.2.2. X-ray powder diffractometry

The phase composition and crystallinity were analyzed using X-ray powder diffractometry (XRD). Data were obtained using an XRD instrument AERIS (Malvern PANalytical, the Netherlands) with Cu Kα radiation (produced at 40 kV and 15 mA). The scan range was 10–70° 2θ, the step size was 0.021°, and the counting time was 37.995 s. The XRD patterns were matched to stoichiometric HAp (International Centre for Diffraction Data (ICDD) card number 01–072–1243).

The degree of crystallinity of the HAp and ZnHAp powders was calculated using diffraction peaks (112) at 32.5° and (300) at 33° of HAp with Eq. 1:

$$X_c = 1 - \frac{V_{112}}{I_{300}} \cdot 100, \quad (1)$$

where X_c is the fraction of the crystalline phase, I_{300} is the intensity of the (300) diffraction peak, and $V_{112/300}$ is the intensity of the well between (112) and (300) diffraction peaks of HAp.

2.2.3. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

The molecular composition was analyzed using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). Data were obtained using an FTIR instrument Nicolet IS50 FT-IR (Thermo Fisher, USA) equipped with the attenuated reflectance (ATR) sample module (IS50 ATR Nicolet (Thermo Fisher, USA). Absorbance was measured over the 400–4000 cm⁻¹ range at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, co-adding 64 scans per sample.

2.2.4. Scanning electron microscopy

The morphology of the HAp and ZnHAp powders was evaluated using high-resolution scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The images were captured using an SEM Verios 5 UC (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA) microscope. The microscope was operated in transmission mode at an acceleration voltage of 20 kV, and the scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) detector was utilized to capture bright-field (BF) images. To conduct microscopy measurements, the powder samples were mixed with ethanol, stirred in an ultrasonic condition for 15 min, left for 15 min before being transferred to a carbon grid (221MLC20, Micro to Nano, The Netherlands), and dried at 40 °C for 24 h.

2.2.5. N₂ adsorption

The specific surface area (SSA_{BET}) of the HAp and ZnHAp powders was measured using the N₂ adsorption method and the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) model. The measurements were performed using a Quadrasorb SI/Kr (Quantachrome Instruments, FL, USA) surface area and pore size analyzer. Before analysis, approximately 0.2 g of the powders were degassed for 24 h at 25 °C with an Autosorb Degasser (Quantachrome Instruments, FL, USA). Three measurements per batch were performed. The measured SSA_{BET} values were used to calculate the

mean particle size (d_{BET}) under the hypothesis of the spherical particle using Eq. 2:

$$d_{BET} = \frac{6}{SSA_{BET} \cdot \rho} \quad (2)$$

where ρ - the true density of the powders measured using He pycnometer Micro UltraPyc™ 1200e (Quantachrome Instruments, FL, USA). Approximately 2 g of the powder was weighed into the analysis cell. The mode with 30 gas pulsations was used for the measurements, and the average value was calculated from 5 consecutive measurements, the standard deviation of which was 0.1. Three measurements per batch were performed.

Zeta potential was determined using a Litesizer 500 light-scattering instrument for particle analysis (Anton Paar, USA). The 10 mg of the powders were suspended in 1 mL of the 0.154 M NaCl (physiological saline) or TSB. The zeta potentials of three parallel samples were measured by averaging 100 runs under an applied voltage of 20 kV.

2.3. Microbiological testing

2.3.1. Antibacterial activity

Reference bacterial cultures - *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*, ATCC 14209) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*, ATCC 27698) - were used for the antibacterial activity assessment. Each bacterial culture was grown on a trypticase soy agar (TSA, Liofilchem, Italy) plate at 35 °C for 18 ± 2 h. The bacterial suspensions in trypticase soy broth (TSB, Oxoid Ltd, UK) were prepared with a density of 0.5 units according to the McFarland standard. To ascertain the bacterial density of the initial inoculums at 0.5 McFarland standard, bacterial suspensions at 0.5 McFarland standard were prepared and diluted to subsequently plate the final dilutions onto TSA plates. The plates were incubated at 35 °C for 18 ± 2 h, and colonies were counted using a bacterial colony counter BZG30 (WTW, Germany). The final bacterial concentrations at 0.5 McFarland standard of the initial inoculums for further experiments were 9.0•10⁵ CFU/mL for *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 14209 and 2.1•10⁶ CFU/mL for *S. aureus* ATCC 27698.

In centrifuge tubes, 0.1 g of autoclaved HAp and ZnHAp powders were weighed, and 10 mL of bacterial suspension was added. Sterile TSB was used as a negative control, and bacterial suspension without powder was used as a positive control. All samples were made in duplicate. The samples were incubated for 8 h, 16 h, 32 h, and 72 h in a rotating table incubator Infors™ HT (Ecotron CA, USA) at 35 °C under dynamic conditions at 150 rpm. After each incubation period, the tubes were stirred by gently inverting them several times, and serial tenfold dilutions were made in a sterile 0.9 % NaCl solution. Depending on the expected number of colonies, 10 μL of the respective tenfold dilution was spread on a TSA plate. These steps were also duplicated, resulting in four replicates of each sample. After drying, the plates were reversed (with the lids down) and incubated at 35 °C for 18 ± 2 h. After incubation, colonies were counted using the bacterial colony counter. The number of bacterial colony-forming units (CFU/mL) was calculated using Eq. 3:

$$CFU / mL = \frac{\text{Number of colonies} \cdot \text{Dilution factor}}{\text{Volume}} \quad (3)$$

2.3.2. Phage adsorption

Lytic bacteriophage reference stocks - *P. aeruginosa* bacteriophage (ATCC 14209-B1, bacteriophage suspension titer 1.07•10¹⁰ PFU/mL) and *S. aureus* bacteriophage (ATCC 27698-B1, bacteriophage suspension titer 3.55•10⁷ PFU/mL) and the respective host bacterial cultures - *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 14209 and *S. aureus* ATCC 27698 were used.

Powders and phage mixtures were prepared, where the concentration of the powders was 0.01 g/mL. Sterile TSB was used as a negative control, and bacterial suspensions were used as a positive control. All samples were prepared in duplicate and incubated in a rotary table incubator at 35 °C for 24 h under dynamic conditions at 150 rpm. After

incubation for 12, 24, and 72 h, the resulting suspensions were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 3 min at room temperature. The phage titer was determined in the sediments and the liquid phase (suspensions). After decantation, 1 mL of sterile TSB was added to the sediments to determine the phage titer in the sediments. Tenfold serial dilutions of the resulting suspensions were made in a sterile 0.9 % NaCl solution to achieve a practically countable number of plaques (10–100 plaques). In a 15 mL tube, 50 μ L of the respective dilution of the prepared suspensions and 100 μ L of the host bacterial suspension were added. The host bacterial culture was grown on a TSA plate at 35 °C for 18 \pm 2 h, from which 3–5 colonies were taken and incubated in TSB at 35 °C for 4 h in a rotating table incubator under dynamic conditions at 150 rpm to acquire active growing bacterial cells. Pre-melted 5–7 mL semi-liquid TSA (70 %, *Liofilchem*, Italy) was mixed into each tube. The contents of the tubes were poured onto TSA plates. When the freshly poured top layer dried, the plates were reversed (with the lids down) and incubated at 35 °C for 18 \pm 2 h. After incubation, the plaques were counted using a bacterial colony counter. These steps were duplicated, resulting in four replicates for each sample. Phage titer (PFU/mL) was calculated using Eq. 4:

$$PFU / mL = \frac{\text{Number of plaques} \cdot \text{Dilution factor}}{\text{Volume}} \quad (4)$$

2.3.3. Statistical analysis

All results were expressed as the mean value \pm standard deviation (SD) of at least three measurements. Statistical analysis was performed using One-way ANOVA with the significance level set at $p < 0.05$ (ns - > 0.05 , * - for $p < 0.05$, ** - for $p < 0.01$, *** - for $p < 0.001$).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physicochemical characterization of the HAp and ZnHAp nanoparticles

The attention was devoted to evaluating the effect of Zn content on the physicochemical properties of HAp nanoparticles before and after autoclaving. Although substituted HAp has been studied relatively frequently, the influence of sterilization on product properties has rarely been critically evaluated, even though it is of crucial importance for practical applications.

The chemical composition of the synthesis products was analyzed to confirm the presence of Zn in them (Table 2).

The ICP-MS analysis confirmed the presence of Zn in the synthesis products. The measured Zn concentration in the as-synthesized powders and calculated Zn/(Ca+Zn) of the as-synthesized powders were close to the nominal values. The as-synthesized powders' Ca/P and (Ca+Zn)/P molar ratios were much lower than the stoichiometric Ca/P molar ratio of 1.67 for HAp. Moreover, with increasing Zn concentration, the Ca/P

Table 2

The measured Zn concentration in the synthesis products before and after autoclaving.

Sample series		HAp	1ZnHAp	2ZnHAp
Nominal Zn/(Ca+Zn), %		-	1	2
As-synthesized powders	Zn concentration, wt %	-	0.40	0.79
			± 0.04	± 0.08
	Zn/(Ca+Zn)	-	1	2
	Ca/P molar ratio	1.47	1.46	1.42
	(Ca+Zn)/P molar ratio	1.47	1.47	1.43
Autoclaved powders	Zn concentration, wt %	-	0.35	0.74
			± 0.04	± 0.07
	Zn/(Ca+Zn)	-	1	2
	Ca/P molar ratio	1.64	1.61	1.61
	(Ca+Zn)/P molar ratio	1.64	1.62	1.63

molar ratio decreased. However, the (Ca+Zn)/P molar ratio of the ZnHAp powders was higher than the Ca/P molar ratio due to the presence of Zn. The effect of autoclaving on the Zn concentration in the synthesis products was insignificant. The autoclaved powders' Ca/P and (Ca+Zn)/P molar ratios increased and approached the stoichiometric HAp's Ca/P molar ratio, i.e., 1.67. As a low Ca/P ratio is usually associated with a disordered crystal structure, it can be suggested that the recrystallization occurred during autoclaving, which promoted the formation of the HAp with higher crystallinity [19].

XRD and ATR-FTIR were used to analyze phase and molecular composition to characterize the changes due to Zn addition and autoclaving. Fig. 1(A) shows the XRD patterns in the 25° to 45° range, where the most relevant diffraction maxima of HAp are diffracted.

The detected XRD peaks corresponded to the ICDD database entry No. 01-072-1234 for the HAp reference XRD pattern. The broad XRD peaks suggested the relatively low crystallinity degree of the obtained products, as summarized in Table 3.

Increasing Zn concentration in the synthesis media caused a decrease in the crystallinity of the synthesis products, as evidenced by the broadening and merging of the characteristic diffraction maxima, particularly the triplet in the 2 θ region from 30–35° (e.g., diffraction maxima (211) and (112)). The observed correlated with previously reported findings that incorporating vicarious ions in the HAp lattice causes structural changes, affecting the material's physicochemical properties such as crystal structure, crystallinity, surface charge, solubility, etc. [20]. Therefore, a decrease in crystallinity is associated with incorporating Zn into the HAp lattice. Autoclaving increased the crystallinity of the synthesis products, as evidenced by the narrowing and splitting of the diffraction maxima. Thus, autoclaving, i.e., an elevated temperature in a saturated steam atmosphere, led to their partial dissolution followed by re-precipitation, which promoted the growth of the HAp crystallites [21].

Fig. 1(B) shows the ATR-FTIR spectra in the 400–1200 cm^{-1} range, where the characteristic absorbance bands of the HAp are observed. The formation of the HAp phase was confirmed by the [PO₄] groups' characteristic absorbance bands at 472 (ν_2), 560–600 (ν_4), 959–1096 (ν_3) cm^{-1} and [OH] groups' absorbance bands at 625 and 3569 cm^{-1} [22]. In the ATR-FTIR spectra, the transition from a poorly crystalline HAp into a well-crystallized HAp is accompanied by a gradual splitting of the [PO₄] absorbance groups at 600 cm^{-1} (ν_4) and at 1100 cm^{-1} (ν_3). Thus, the ATR-FTIR spectra confirmed that the autoclaving increased the crystallinity of the powders.

The SEM analysis confirmed that Zn concentration and autoclaving modified the shape and size of the HAp nanoparticles (Fig. 2).

SEM images of the as-synthesized powders showed agglomerated nanoparticles of heterogeneous sizes with needle-like morphology (with pointed ends) (Fig. 2(A-C)). With the addition of Zn, the morphology of particles changed; namely, the higher the Zn content, the finer the particles become. The observed changes in particle morphology indicate the incorporation of Zn into the HAp crystal lattice [23]. As a result of autoclaving, the particles have strongly agglomerated and become wider, showing a rod-like morphology (with rounded ends) (Fig. 2 (D-F)). This observation is related to the described effect of autoclaving on HAp crystallinity.

In addition, the SSA_{BET} of the powders was measured, and the d_{BET} was calculated (Table 3). With increasing the concentration of Zn in the powders, the SSA_{BET} of the as-synthesized and autoclaved powders increased. As a result of autoclaving, the SSA_{BET} of the as-synthesized and autoclaved powders decreased. The opposite was observed for the mean particle sizes (d_{BET}) calculated using SSA_{BET} and true density values (ρ). The increase in SSA_{BET} and decrease in d_{BET} can be explained by the incorporation of Zn²⁺ ions with a smaller radius (0.74 Å) in the HAp crystal lattice, replacing Ca²⁺ ions with a larger radius (0.99 Å) and deforming the HAp crystal lattice, limiting crystallite growth [24]. These observations correlated with the XRD data, X_c calculations, and SEM images.

Fig. 1. A – the XRD patterns and B – the ATR-FTIR spectra of the as-synthesized and autoclaved HAp and ZnHAp powders.

Table 3

The degree of crystallinity (X_C), SSA_{BET} , and mean particle size (d_{BET}) of the as-synthesized and autoclaved HAp and ZnHAp powders.

Sample series	As-synthesized			Autoclaved		
	X_C , %	SSA_{BET} , m^2/g	d_{BET} , nm	X_C , %	SSA_{BET} , m^2/g	d_{BET} , nm
HAp	40	61.9 ± 1.1	34.2 ± 0.6	60	40.9 ± 0.5	51.7 ± 0.8
1ZnHAp	29	72.9 ± 1.4	29.3 ± 0.4	49	50.5 ± 1.7	42.0 ± 1.4
2ZnHAp	24	75.5 ± 0.8	28.2 ± 0.2	39	57.1 ± 1.7	36.8 ± 0.8

HAp nanoparticles interact with phages, which is possible due to surface adsorption and should be performed at the final stage of material development. The surface adsorption is based on differences in zeta potential (negative for most phages and positive for HAp) [9]. The zeta potential of the as-synthesized nanoparticles in 0.154 M NaCl was 3.71 ± 1.11 mV (HAp), 4.23 ± 2.16 mV (1ZnHAp), and 5.15 ± 0.78 mV (2ZnHAp), and in the TSB, it was -23.38 ± 2.01 mV (HAp), -23.33 ± 1.31 mV (1ZnHAp), and -25.11 ± 1.48 mV (2ZnHAp). Our results contradict the literature data suggesting that HAp has a negative zeta potential in neutral (physiological) pH, and its magnitude depends on the substituent ions [25–28]. The negative charge of HAp is attributed to the presence of $[PO_4]$ and $[OH]$ groups [28]. Moreover, Fahami et al. observed that substituting the PO_4^{3-} ions with Cl^- or F^- ions provides a more negative zeta potential [25]. However, the zeta potential as a

physical characteristic exhibited by any particle in suspension, macromolecule, or material surface also depends on the medium in which the nanoparticles are suspended. The zeta potential of the HAp and ZnHAp nanoparticles and the TSB mixture was negative. TSB contains casein, soy digests (proteins), glucose, and sodium chloride [29]. It has been reported that the zeta potential of the component of TSB is negative, i.e., soy protein is approximately -25 mV [30]. Therefore, it can be concluded that the proteins in the TSB composition determine the zeta potential of the HAp and ZnHAp nanoparticles and TSB mixtures.

3.2. Antibacterial properties of the HAp and ZnHAp nanoparticles

The antibacterial activity of the autoclaved HAp and ZnHAp nanoparticles against Gram-negative *P. aeruginosa* (Fig. 3(A)) and Gram-positive *S. aureus* (Fig. 3(B)) bacteria after incubation for 8, 16, 32, and 72 h was evaluated.

After 8 and 16 h of incubation, the concentration of Gram-negative *P. aeruginosa* bacteria in the powder-bacteria suspensions was higher than in the control, suggesting no antibacterial activity against the Gram-negative *P. aeruginosa*. After 32 h of incubation, a slightly lower concentration of *P. aeruginosa* bacteria was observed in the case of ZnHAp nanoparticles compared with the control and HAp nanoparticles. However, the growth of bacteria increased again after 72 h. Overall, it can be concluded that the HAp and ZnHAp nanoparticles did not have antibacterial activity against *P. aeruginosa* bacteria.

Regarding *S. aureus* bacteria, the CFU increased for all samples up to 32 h of incubation. By increasing the incubation time to 72 h, the HAp and ZnHAp nanoparticles almost halved the CFU of *S. aureus*, while it

Fig. 2. The SEM images of the A, D - HAp, B, E - 1ZnHAp, and C, F - 2ZnHAp as-synthesized (A, B, C) and autoclaved (D, E, F) powders.

Fig. 3. The antibacterial activity of the autoclaved HAp and ZnHAp powders against A - *P. aeruginosa* and B - *S. aureus* (One-way ANOVA, (ns - > 0.05, * - for $p < 0.05$, ** - for $p < 0.01$, *** - for $p < 0.001$).

continued to grow in the control sample. Increasing the concentration of Zn in the nanoparticles decreased the CFU, confirming the antibacterial effect of Zn^{2+} ions against Gram-positive *S. aureus* bacteria. Interestingly, the HAp nanoparticles also had an antibacterial effect on *S. aureus*

bacteria. This could be due to the nano size of the particles, which facilitates their binding to microorganisms, inducing the death of the bacterial cell [31,32].

To sum up, the antibacterial activity of the HAp and ZnHAp

Fig. 4. Titer of *P. aeruginosa* phages after incubation in the presence of HAp and ZnHAp nanoparticles for A - 12, B - 24, and C - 72 h, and titer of *S. aureus* phages after incubation in the presence of the HAp and ZnHAp nanoparticles for D - 12, E - 24, and F - 72 h.

nanoparticles depended on the incubation time and the species of bacteria, confirming the more substantial antibacterial effect of Zn^{2+} ions against Gram-positive bacteria. However, it is relatively negligible or non-existent against Gram-negative bacteria. This is explained by the resistance of general Gram-negative bacteria to antibacterial agents due to their cell wall structure [33,34].

3.3. Interaction of the HAp and ZnHAp nanoparticles with phages

To prepare the HAp-phage and ZnHAp-phage complexes, it is crucial to understand whether the phages retain their lytic activity after incubation in the presence of the powders. Considering the different effects of the HAp and ZnHAp nanoparticles on *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* bacteria, two different phages, namely, with lytic activity against *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* bacteria, were assessed. The titer of the *P. aeruginosa* phages and *S. aureus* phages in the suspensions and the sediments (powders) after 12, 24, and 72 h of incubation, indicating the concentration of the lytic phages, is shown in Fig. 4.

The *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* phages retained their lytic activity after incubation with the HAp and ZnHAp nanoparticles. However, the phage titer decreased compared to the stock phage suspensions. The titer of *P. aeruginosa* phages decreased after 12 h incubation and slightly increased after 24 h incubation with the HAp and 1ZnHAp nanoparticles. The phage titer decreased gradually after the *P. aeruginosa* phages were incubated with the 2ZnHAp nanoparticles. After 72 h of incubation, the *P. aeruginosa* phage titer decreased in all samples. Analogous phenomena to those above were observed when evaluating the effects of incubation time and the nanoparticles on the lytic activity of the *S. aureus* phages. Thus, when preparing HAp or ZnHAp-phage complexes, the interaction time between nanoparticles and phages must be carefully selected to maintain high phage lytic activity. In the case of *P. aeruginosa* phages, the optimal time among those studied is 24 h, and *S. aureus* phages 12 h.

The titer of the lytic phages in the sediments was a hundredfold lower than in the respective suspensions. This indicates that phage binding to nanoparticles is low. However, the achieved phage titer in the sediments is medium (10^6 – 10^7), which could be sufficient for local phage therapy [35]. Considering such promising benefits of lyophilized hydroxyapatite-phage complexes as enhanced stability, consistent dosing, and optimized delivery, Decodts et al. have executed antibacterial activity, phage release profile, and biofilm assays with phage-impregnated and phage-encapsulated powders [36]. In our study, phage titers in both phage suspension and sediments after decantation were evaluated and compared to analyze phage binding to nanoparticles and optimize the formula for the delivery of phage treatment, establishing the foundation for the practical application of hydroxyapatite-phage systems.

Moreover, the phage titer decreased with increasing the Zn concentration in the nanoparticles; namely, the phage titer was lower after incubation with the 1ZnHAp and 2ZnHAp nanoparticles. Previous studies on the interaction of HAp nanoparticles and phages have shown beneficial effects. It has been reported that the complex of HAp nanoparticles and *Salmonella* bacteriophages (SR ϕ 1) show higher antibacterial activity than the phage alone [10]. Andriolo et al. have described the enhancement of the iron-doped apatite nanoparticles on phage's ability to infect nonpathogenic bacteria and pathogenic strains [37]. The discrepancy between the results obtained in our study and the literature data could be due to the presence of Zn. Namely, a significant decrease in phage titer due to the presence of Zn^{2+} ions in the incubation medium has been observed by Weglewska et al. [38].

Although ZnHAp does not affect *P. aeruginosa* bacterial cell growth or colony formation, *P. aeruginosa* bacterial cells experience increased death in the presence of the phages. For that reason, the results demonstrate that combining alternative antimicrobial agents (metallic ions and phages) of different origins makes obtaining HAp nanoparticles with multitarget effects possible. These results are, therefore, promising

for antibacterial applications in biomedicine.

4. Conclusions

Phase-pure nanosized hydroxyapatite with a zinc content of 0, 0.35 \pm 0.04, and 0.74 \pm 0.07 wt% was obtained using wet chemical precipitation followed by autoclaving (sterilization in saturated water steam (120 °C, 20 min)). Increasing the zinc content lowered the degree of crystallinity of hydroxyapatite, increased the specific surface area, and reduced the average particle size. Autoclaving increased the crystallinity of synthesis products, lowered the specific surface area, and promoted changes in morphology from needle-like to rod-like. Hydroxyapatite containing 0, 0.35 \pm 0.04, and 0.74 \pm 0.07 wt% of zinc did not show antibacterial activity against Gram-negative *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* bacteria. Zinc-substituted hydroxyapatite showed time- and concentration-dependent antibacterial activity against Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria. The incubation of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* phages with zinc-substituted hydroxyapatite nanoparticles resulted in a negligible decrease in phage titer. The loss of phage lytic activity was caused by increased zinc concentration in the hydroxyapatite nanoparticles and incubation time. Phage adsorption or binding to the nanoparticles was low and would require advanced techniques, such as applying binding agents, to improve it. Overall, the results confirmed that the use of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* phages in combination with zinc-substituted hydroxyapatite nanoparticles is a promising technique for obtaining complexes with polymicrobial involving both Gram-positive and Gram-negative microorganisms (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) infections' prevention and treatment. This initial characterization of how zinc-substituted hydroxyapatite nanoparticles affect phages provides promise for future work to develop antibacterial hydroxyapatite-phage complexes for therapeutic and antibacterial applications. Furthermore, as the underlying cause of resistant implant-related infections is primarily due to biofilm formation, the potential antibiofilm effect of hydroxyapatite-phage complexes is of great interest, fostering inquiry for prospective research.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dace Rezevska: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Liga Stipniece:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lelde Rubene:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Marika Scegllova:** Investigation, Data curation. **Sandis Maurins:** Investigation, Data curation. **Renats Vasiljevs:** Investigation, Data curation. **Karlis Racenis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology. **Juta Kroica:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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